

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

Workflow and piloting for retrieval and harmonisation of Remote Sensing data and products

Deliverable D4.3

20 November 2023

Author(s) and affiliations:

Micha Silver¹, Carmela Marangi², Diego Garcia-Diaz³, Alessandro Oggioni², Paolo Tagliolato², Arnon Karnieli¹, Ricardo Diaz-Delgado³, Johannes Peterseil⁴, Saverio Vicario¹, Saku Anttila⁵, Will Bolton⁶, Christoph Wohner⁴, Ivo Offenthaler⁴, Vladan Minić⁷

¹Ben Gurion University, Israel

²CNR, Italy

³CSIC, Spain

⁴Umweltbundesamt GmbH, Austria

⁵Syke, Finland

⁶UK Centre of Ecology and Hydrology, UK

⁷BioSense

Contribution to the work and the report

All people listed as authors contributed to the textual description of the report. Chapter authors are given, where appropriate. Authors and contributing authors contributed to the implementation of the task in collecting the information on the data sources, participation at working meetings and in defining the scope of the report and the demonstrators.

Internal reviewers and affiliation

(in alphabetical order)

Jaana Bäck (UH)

Ulf Mallast (UFZ)

Allan T. Souza (UH)

Prepared under contract from the European Commission
 Grant agreement No. 871128
 EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action

Project acronym: **eLTER PLUS**
 Project full title: European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure PLUS
 Start of the project: Feb 2020
 Duration: 60 months
 Website: <https://www.lter-europe.net/projects/elter-plus>

Deliverable title: Workflow and piloting for retrieval and harmonisation of Remote Sensing data and products
 Deliverable n°: D4.3
 Nature of the deliverable: [Report, Demonstrator]
 Dissemination level: [Public]

Citation: Silver, M., Marangi, C., Garcia-Diaz, D., Oggioni, A., Tagliolato, P., Karnieli, A., Diaz-Delgado, R., Peterseil, J., Vicario, S., Anttila, S., Bolton, W., Wohner, C., Offenthaler, I., Minić, V., (2023). "Workflow and piloting for retrieval and harmonisation of Remote Sensing data and products". Deliverable D4.3 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128. 35 pp.

Deliverable status:

Version	Status	Date	Author(s)
0.1	Draft	10 December 2022	Micha Silver (BGU)
0.10	Draft for review	30 May 2023	Arnon Karnieli and Micha Silver (BGU)
0.11	First revised version	16 August 2023	Carmela Marangi and co-authors
1.0	Final	20 November 2023	Carmela Marangi and co-authors

The content of this deliverable does not necessarily reflect the official opinions of the European Commission or other institutions of the European Union.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	eLTER Data Needs and Requirements	11
3	Components of the eLTER Information System	13
3.1	Digital Asset Register (DAR) overview	13
3.2	DEIMS-SDR overview	13
3.3	EnvThes overview	14
3.4	DataLabs overview	14
3.5	EcoSense overview.....	14
4	Identification of data sources.....	16
5	Piloting retrieval of Remote Sensing data and products: a “static” view of the workflow	18
5.1	Static view: regular provision of selected variables.....	19
6	Piloting retrieval Remote Sensing data and products: a “dynamical” view of the workflow ..	22
6.1	Tools: GeeLTERMap	23
6.1.1	PhenoApp.....	24
6.1.2	FloodApp.....	25
6.1.3	LSTApp.....	26
6.1.4	FormApp.....	27
6.1.5	Implementation in DataLabs and usage	28
6.1.5.1	PyVPP	28
6.1.5.2	Ndvi2Gif	29
6.2	Tools: CrocoTile.....	31
6.3	Tools: ReLTER.....	33
7	Demonstrations and capacity building.....	36
7.1	PhenoApp demonstration.....	36
7.2	ReLTER demonstration.....	36
8	Future development	38
8.1	PhenoApp - GeeLterMap	38
8.2	ReLTER.....	38
9	Conclusions	39
10	References	40

Glossary

API	Application Programming Interface
B2DROP	EUDAT B2DROP service, based on NextCloud
B2SHARE	EUDAT B2SHARE publication service, based on Invenio issuing DOIs
BDL	Research challenge Biodiversity loss
BGC	Research challenge Bio-geochemical processes
CDN	eLTER Central Data Node
CLC	Corine Land Cover
csv	Comma-separated values
CWF	Research challenge Climate-Water-Food-Nexus
DAR	eLTER Digital Asset Registry
DataLab	eLTER Data Laboratory
DEIMS.ID	DEIMS-SDR (persistent site) identifier
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information System - Site and Dataset Registry
DIP	eLTER Data Integration Platform
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
EnvThes	Environmental thesaurus
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
IC	eLTER Information Clusters
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IS	eLTER Information System
netCDF	netCDF file
PID	(Unique) Persistent Identifier
RC	Research Challenges
RI	Research Infrastructure
SC	Science cases
SES	Research challenge Socio-ecological systems
SO	eLTER Standard Observations

SOS	OGC Sensor Observation Service
SWE	OGC Sensor Web Enablement
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
UML	Unified Modelling Language

Summary

A qualifying objective of future eLTER research is to strive for the whole-system approach covering all spheres involved in current ecosystem and ecosystem service studies, from the atmosphere to the geosphere and the hydrosphere, from the biosphere to the socio-economic sphere. This requires data from all available sources to broaden the thematic, spatial, and temporal scope and to fill gaps in the information collected directly at eLTER in-situ facilities. The concept of Information Clusters supports this approach by developing a framework to facilitate access to and exchange of data and information coming from multiple sources that complement eLTER in-situ observations. The implementation of "Information Clusters" will be achieved by identifying three primary data sources: (a) legacy data, also including archive data collected at eLTER facilities and provided by third parties, (b) official statistics data provided by statistical offices from national to pan-European and global levels, and (c) remote sensing (RS) data, and products.

The primary emphasis of this report is placed on the final portion of the data landscape of interest, i.e. the one related to remote sensing data and products. Similar to how strategies and workflows were previously outlined for both legacy data and official statistics, this report now proceeds to describe the approaches and procedures developed for obtaining variables derived from remote sensing and potentially contributing to eLTER Standard Observations, such as NDVI, albedo, land surface temperature, and land cover change. The report summarises the development of user-friendly and harmonised methods for retrieving remote sensing data and products at different scales and from different archives and repositories (e.g., Copernicus, USGS/NASA, and others).

1 Introduction

Carmela Marangi and Micha Silver

In the past few years, there has been a notable growth in observatory networks and improved accessibility to observed data. This has greatly enhanced our capacity to observe and understand the changes and pressures impacting ecosystems and ecosystem services. These observatory networks operate continuously, delivering quality controlled and regularly updated information, thereby playing a vital role in implementing EU and national directives aimed at conserving and restoring ecosystems as well as harmonising economic development with sustainability.

The provision of openly shared and easily accessible standardised and harmonised *in-situ* data from a network of facilities is one of the primary goals of the future eLTER RI. Moreover, eLTER RI aims to address the major environmental challenges by establishing a well-connected community of experts working to translate research questions into actionable knowledge and ensuring adaptation to fast-evolving scenarios.

The complexity of the research challenges addressed by the eLTER community demands for a multidisciplinary effort and availability of types and quantities of data that are usually beyond the expertise and resources of individual communities. Third-party data are often necessary to complement *in-situ* observations for different purposes, e.g., gap-filling, cross-scale analysis, distributed experiments, and connectivity analysis. Data from multiple sources become increasingly relevant to complement, integrate or surrogate parameters measured in the field and enable the scientific community to continuously broaden the thematic, spatial, and temporal scope of ecological and socio-ecological research conducted at sites and cross-site. Within the eLTER community, this process is consistently amplified by the holistic view pursued through the eLTER Whole System Approach, which encompasses the Earth system and related domains/disciplines from the geosphere to the hydrosphere, from biosphere to atmosphere, to social and economic sphere.

An additional challenge is posed by the recent Destination Earth initiative, which aims to build a digital Earth model to understand better and control the factors that influence nature conservation and human health and well-being. As for the Whole System Approach, the new paradigm can be applied only if we can guarantee a continuous flow of standardised and harmonised information from various research domains, networks, and infrastructures. Hence, the demand for data from multiple and heterogeneous information sources, as well as the strategies for their integration at different scales, evolve in quantity and quality at an increasing pace.

That notwithstanding, a closer look at the kaleidoscopic landscape of data provisioning for environmental research suggests that the exploitation of such information richness is a trivial task. Each data source provides its products with different access rules, formats, licensing conditions, coverage, and resolution in time and space. As a result, the collection of multiple sources' data and its integration is often perceived as a barrier to further scientific development.

For this reason, a relevant part of the eLTER PLUS project activities aims to ensure access to multiple and external data sources and lower the technical barriers that hamper data exploitation from different disciplinary domains. Harmonising and integrating third party's data with eLTER Standard Observations (see D3.1 "Discussion paper on eLTER Standard Observations (eLTER SOs)") from *in-situ* measurements allows to generate high level data products for advanced research and knowledge-informed decision-making.

In eLTER PLUS, the collection, harmonisation, and integration of data and information from multiple sources are defined by the "Information Cluster" concept, which represents the operational answer that eLTER PLUS provides to the challenges of the emerging RI framework. The main idea behind the concept of information clusters is to simplify the harvesting and user uptake of data from multiple

information sources, facilitating the integration with eLTER data and making the best use of existing services, e.g., the ones provided by Copernicus. The selection of sources and content of the relevant data layers results from an internal discussion where the Research Challenges play the main role by identifying the current trends of the environmental research and the ensuing demand for external data. The process is informed by the overarching frame provided by the eLTER Standard SOs. Figure 1 illustrates the Information Clusters' role in the eLTER PLUS project context.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the role of the eLTER Information Clusters in the project context.

For the eLTER PLUS project, as informed by the Research Challenges, implementing the Information Clusters concept led to the identification of 3 different data categories of interest: legacy data, official statistics, and remote sensing data and products. The first two categories, their main sources, and the related workflows have already been described in two project deliverables (D4.1 “Workflow for retrieval and harmonisation of legacy data” by J. Peterseil et al., D4.2 “Workflow for retrieval and harmonisation of data from official statistics” by L. Halada et al.), one for each category.

The activities described in this report focus on the last data type, i.e., facilitating access to Remote Sensing (RS) data for researchers working in the eLTER RI community. An important feature of this category of data is that it provides a wide range and variety of spatially explicit data covering large regions. Environmental and ecological research done at the eLTER facilities often requires a spatial coverage extending beyond the official boundaries of the sites. Over the past decade, RS data archives have expanded exponentially (Wulder et al. 2012, Vitor, et al. 2020), offering researchers huge archives of time-varying spatial data spanning a broad spectral range and at differing spatial resolutions. The current work focuses on two approaches to the provision of RS data products, also referred to as different views of how the RI can build a service on the provision of RS data products. The deliverable illustrates these views, defined in the followings as “static” and “dynamical”, respectively. That is done by designing the relative data workflows and describing the tools that have

been developed to enable researchers in the fields of ecology and environment to obtain and make use of RS data.

For the sake of completeness, in the following two sections we set the scene where the RS data workflows are positioned, by briefly recalling the process used to define the data needs and the components of the on-build cyberinfrastructure where the workflows must be mapped.

2 eLTER Data Needs and Requirements

Carmela Marangi

The analysis of data needs and requirements has been the core activity of the first year of the project and constitutes the background knowledge for the design of the services of the future infrastructure. It started with the definition of the research needs of the eLTER network in order to identify the variables that would serve those needs as well as the relative data requirements in terms of e.g., range, resolution, format. To this end, eLTER PLUS organised the activities around the major research challenges (RCs) and science cases (SCs) addressed by the community. Four RCs have already been selected at the stage of defining the project work plan, namely (a) Biodiversity Loss (BDL), (b) Biogeochemical controls of ecosystem functions (BGC), (c) Climate-water-food nexus (CWF), and (d) Socio-ecological systems (SES). These RCs cover most of the current activities of the project and of the RI, and they are at the basis of the selection of the eLTER SOs. A preliminary analysis was performed in the first months of the project, to identify the variables relevant to each Research Challenge along with the data requirements at both site and pan-European scale. This activity is reported in two deliverables (D8.5, Skiba, U. et al., 2020, D9.5, Dirnböck, T. et al., 2020) addressing the two relevant scales mentioned above. The two reports illustrate the results of a community survey analysing long-term data made available by the eLTER community and include a brief description of the science cases which motivated the data collection and use. The main outcome of the survey is the identification of 98 variables grouped according to their thematic scope that goes from biodiversity to climate, from soil to water, and from land use to socio-economy. For each data (variable) type, the unit of measure, as well as the temporal resolution, have been specified together with information about the science case that the data type relates to. This information has been then further elaborated to generate the list of eLTER SOs, i.e., the observations that will enter the regular data provision of the future RI. eLTER SOs have been divided into three large groups (sensor-based, sample-based, retrieval-based) corresponding to variables observed by sensors deployed at the sites if the observations result from in-field observations, by sampling if the data originates from a set of physical samples analysed, or the datasets come from retrieval of third-party data. The final list of SOs, comprises 173 SOs further grouped according to the thematic scope with respect to the different spheres (geosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, atmosphere, sociosphere). More details are provided in the report “*Discussion paper on eLTER Standard Observations (eLTER SOs)(version 2)*” (in Zacharias et al., 2022).

Noteworthy is the fact that the compilation of Strategic Objectives (SOs) stems from an extensive and inclusive discussion and consultation with eLTER research community, National coordinators and the project beneficiaries. This dialogue was formally initiated at the outset of the eLTER PLUS project, yet it also draws upon insights from previous projects and research undertakings. The progression of this process entailed iterative consultations that encompassed the entire community, both within and outside the project consortium. This ongoing process continually adjusts to emerging challenges, conditions, and constraints. The effectiveness of the outcome hinges on the collaborative way it was formulated and the extensive engagement of the community in the endeavor. While alternative methods, such as systematic mapping, could be considered for generating the final result, it's imperative to underscore that involving the entire community in the selection of SOs carries a twofold advantage. It not only fosters community cohesion but also generates data provisioning services that are sustainable, affordable, usable and used by the eLTER community. Any data workflow and service design should reflect this feature, but it should at the same time allow for flexibility in adapting to new opportunities or bottlenecks.

The work is still in progress, particularly with regard to retrieved SOS, which were not the main focus of the first iterations of the identification process, since the analysis was primarily focusing on the core service of the infrastructure, specifically the provision of data sourced from observations collected at the eLTER sites. However, as the list of SOs continues to evolve, it increasingly encompasses variables that can either be directly acquired through RS or approximated using RS data. Consequently, the data

requirements initially established for *in-situ* measurements hold significance in the integration of RS data. These requirements can serve as guidance for selecting the most suitable RS proxies and their respective sources, thereby aiding in fine-tuning the design of RS data workflows.

The assessment of data requisites also delves into the matter of harmonization, a process influenced by both research necessities and the availability of data that satisfy those requirements. With regards to RS data, two fundamental scenarios arise:

- 1) In instances where the variable can solely be procured from third-party sources (for instance, "Snow Cover and Depths" obtained as a Copernicus data product), the variable's nomenclature, format, and resolution (thematic, spatial, and temporal) naturally emanate from the data product itself, which serves as the exclusive information source.
- 2) Alternatively, when the variable is measured in the field according to a designated protocol (such as "Leaf Area Index"), RS data products come into play as proxies. They are utilized for tasks like gap filling, broadening spatial coverage, or are juxtaposed with in-situ observations for calibration and validation objectives. In this scenario, the harmonization process significantly hinges on the specific scientific context or the higher-level eLTER data product that the variable contributes to.

These considerations are duly incorporated into thematic services that are presently under development. The overarching objective of these services is to generate consolidated and comprehensive data products that bridge gaps in information and span various scales – from individual sites to the overarching network, from ecosystems to the broader European scale. Central to these services is the use of proper vocabularies and thesaurus, like EnvThes, which might improve the data interoperability.

3 Components of the eLTER Information System

All authors

This section provides an overview of the components of the eLTER Information System that will be used in the following to build a representation of RS data workflow. Those components either document or process research objects or might be used for documenting or managing Research Objects in the future. In-depth description of the LTER IS and its core elements can be found in a deliverable of the eLTER PLUS project (D11.2, Koivula et al., 2020). We are listing here only the components that are already up and running.

In order to facilitate the reader, some components of the eLTER IS which are explicitly involved in the design of the RS data workflow are briefly recalled here with their main functionalities:

- Digital Asset Registry (DAR): web-based catalogue of digital assets;
- DEIMS-SDR: web-based information portal providing the information context for sites and their equipment as well as the research they carry out and, in general, for any workflow/service provided by the future RI;
- EnvThes: a shared controlled vocabulary which harmonises the terminology used to describe data;
- DataLabs: virtual research environment for processing and temporary storage;
- EcoSense: visualisation tool.

All the components will be integrated within cyberinfrastructure, having a Data Integration Platform (DIP) as exclusive gateway for accessing to data and information, all of which housed within a Central Data Node (CDN). Notably, the details pertaining to the development of these final components are currently in progress and fall outside the purview of this current report.

3.1 Digital Asset Register (DAR) overview

The Digital Asset Register (DAR) is a web-based catalogue of digital assets generated by the eLTER community (<https://catalogue.lter-europe.net/elter/documents>). The types of assets include datasets, web services (e.g., OGC WMS/WFS), models and code/computational notebooks (e.g., Jupyter). Other types of assets can be added if requested. A relevant feature of the current implementation is the recording of the provenance of data. The datasets and their sources contribute to the catalogue, providing all the information needed to integrate datasets in higher-level data products. The assets recorded in the DAR can be searched via a faceted search interface and connected to the eLTER sites through DEIMS-SDR. The registry is equipped with all the functionalities supporting the implementation of the FAIR principles. It includes a RESTful API to allow external codes to search, edit and manipulate the metadata of the digital assets. DAR provides search results in various formats, including JSON, XML, and RDF.

3.2 DEIMS-SDR overview

DEIMS-SDR (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry, www.deims.org) is a web-based information portal for integrated ecological research. It allows the discovery of long-term ecosystem research sites around the globe, along with the data gathered at those sites and the people and networks associated with them. DEIMS-SDR describes a wide range of sites, providing information, including each site's location, ecosystems, facilities, parameters measured, and research themes. A growing number of datasets and data products associated with the sites can also be accessed through DEIMS-SDR. All site records are referenced using unique persistent identifiers (PID), called DEIMS.iD, that DEIMS-SDR generates. Searching for sites via keyword, predefined filters or a map search is possible. The available information is exposed through various formats and services. It is the primary site registry for the various LTER networks, most notably ILTER and eLTER (Wohner et al., 2022). As of November 2023, DEIMS-SDR provide information on around

1200 facilities in total or which about 620 are eLTER facilities. It offers different APIs to expose this site information, such as WFS, WMS, CSW, or a REST-API.

Through these APIs, DEIMS information can be shared with others with relative ease, in line with the requirements of the information clusters concept (Peterseil et al., 2022).

3.3 EnvThes overview

The eLTER PLUS project utilises a shared controlled vocabulary known as EnvThes (Schentz et al., 2011, 2013) developed by LTER-Europe, which aims to standardise the terminology used for describing data exchanged within the research infrastructure. Given that naming conventions evolve over time, it is crucial to establish a means of mapping and aligning names and terminologies, not only across different field sites but also within the historical records of each site. To accomplish this task, a web-based vocabulary service hosted by the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology at vocabs.ceh.ac.uk is employed. Metadata authoring tools like DEIMS-SDR and the Digital Asset Registry utilise vocabularies such as EnvThes through the vocabulary service to describe datasets. These standardised terms enable the search for datasets containing similar or related measurements, facilitating data synthesis and analysis as well as increasing data interoperability.

3.4 DataLabs overview

DataLabs is an open collaborative cloud environment for co-designing data methods and workflows, providing a secure area for the collaborative development of tools. It allows the creation of shared drives to store experimental data and shared notebooks to run analysis. DataLabs make it easy to access and analyse research data, whether it is data brought to the lab by the researcher or already available for access via protocols like OpenDAP (Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol) a tool that enables scientists to share data more easily over the internet. DataLabs comes with Spark and Dask built in, allowing to wrap existing R, Python, or Java code in simple statements and to parallelize the run. It is then suited to work on Big Data, speeding up the computation time.

Moreover, it facilitates the creation of an RShiny server inside the data lab and allows exposure results in friendly, easy-to-use web pages. Datalabs is made up of Open-Source projects, allowing community-driven development and support of the tools, increasing the speed of development and lowering costs. In eLTER PLUS DataLabs is currently used to (1) host the data generated by the project pilots for retrieving third parties data; (2) perform the clipping of the third parties data to the border of the sites; (3) perform harmonisation of the data to eLTER standard Data Format; and (4) generate virtual labs to develop and/or run the tools develop and/or host tools for automating third parties data retrieval

3.5 EcoSense overview

EcoSense (EcoSense 2023) is a visualisation tool that constitutes one of the building blocks of the Data Integration Portal in the eLTER RI. It was initially developed in the H2020 e-shape (e-shape 2019) project based on the AgroSens (Agrosens 2022) platform and further developed to serve the purposes of eLTER. It is a web GIS portal designed for the visualisation of eLTER site metadata (fetched from DEIMS-SDR), time-series data (OGC 2012), and selected RS data products. EcoSense allows the visualisation of research objects from the aforementioned components of the RI. Actually, the majority of available data products originate from third-party data, in particular RS data. Meant initially to visualise only that kind of data products, the current functionalities have been extended to support more data types based on eLTER PLUS project needs (see Deliverable 11.6 “Common tools for data discovery, visualisation and exploitation, specifically of data from WP4 sources and pilots, VA and CS” by Vladan Minic et al. in preparation). The demo version of the tool gives access to some global layers such as Digital Elevation Model (Copernicus DEM 2016), selected SoilGrids layers (SoilGrids 2023) (Figure 2), Copernicus Sentinel2 mission granules, or CORINE Land Cover (CORINE Land Cover 2018)

Figure 2: Screenshot of EcoSense displaying SoilGrids layers (top) and Digital Elevation Model layer (bottom)

This platform aims to enable visualisation of large amounts of data without downloading them. Users may compare data retrieved from different sources and even be able to add their own data source (GeoServer/ArcGIS server or SOS server).

4 Identification of data sources

Carmela Marangi

Identifying the sources of RS data of interest for eLTER RI is by itself a dynamic process and a valuable service which the RI may offer to the community. Figure 3 shows the general workflow for identifying a data source and the procedures to add it to the Digital Asset Registry with all the specifications needed to access the source and use the data products it provides. The coding of the elements in the graph is the following:

- Colour coding: in blue, the boxes represent existing components of the eLTER IS. In orange, the workflow components;
- Each orange box defines a class of actions that might be performed in subtasks;
- The main steps are connected in a decision tree.

Figure 3: General workflow to identify a data source and contribute it to DAR.

Details regarding each class of action can be found in D4.1 (Peterseil et al. 2022), as part of the description of a generic workflow for building information clusters.

Focusing on the data type addressed in this report, it is worth noticing that RS data and products are currently made available by a large number of providers, inside and outside Europe, either public and private and for a large number of fields of application, making it difficult to provide a complete picture of the current landscape. A list of the main providers of public RS data and services of interest for the eLTER community can be extracted from the ESA's website (D3.2, Anttila et al. 2022) and is reported in Table 1. In the general case, access to the service occurs upon registration, and downloading and using the data might be restricted. The landscape of RS data providers is continuously evolving, and the thematic scope is widening. Information about the specific services,

the observed variables, and the spatial and temporal resolution are available on the websites of the providers and are constantly updated with new missions and new data products.

Table 1: The main public RS data and service providers as listed in the ESA's website.

RS data provider	Provider website
ESA	https://earth.esa.int/web/guest/home
ESA-Sentinel	https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/
Sentinel Hub	https://www.sentinel-hub.com/
Eumetsat	http://www.eumetsat.int/website/home/index.html
USGS (Landsat)	http://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/
NOAA	http://www.ospo.noaa.gov/
NASA	https://earthdata.nasa.gov/earth-observation-data
Japan	http://www.eorc.jaxa.jp/en/about/distribution/index.html
China	http://www.cma.gov.cn/en
India	http://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in/bhuvan_links.php

5 Piloting retrieval of Remote Sensing data and products: a “static” view of the workflow

Carmela Marangi

The eLTER PLUS WP4 is devoted to recovering and making available data and information from the eLTER RI and external data sources, including RS observations. Given the extent of the RI, the variety of ecosystems covered, the complexity of the research challenges, and the spectrum of different socio-economic conditions, a preliminary step was to set the priorities and to identify a few pilot sites where this information can be collected and made accessible. It was designed as a step-by-step process where we started from simple variables of common interest on a few sites to extend the information retrieval and generation to more sites and more complex variables for specific research questions. One of the objectives of the first year of the project activities was to define the number and the type of variables to be made available, to demonstrate a possible RS data provision service, and to collect the feedback of the LTER community. A further objective was to pave the way for providing the above data semi-automated and facilitating the visualisation of the information gathered in each cluster.

The starting point of the analysis carried out in WP4 has been the identification of simple variables of common interest, i.e., whose use is recurrent in many research activities performed at the eLTER Facilities (eLTER Sites and eLTER Platforms). Examples are Land Cover, NDVI, and Digital Elevation Models. Part of these variables have well-known sources of known quality and offer some processing tools.

As a result of this preliminary analysis, three simple variables have been selected :

- i. Land Surface Temperature (LST at 1000 m spatial resolution and 8-day temporal resolution);
- ii. NDVI / EVI (NDVI and EVI at 250 m spatial resolution and 16-day temporal resolution)
- iii. Land cover (Landcover from CORINE for the years 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018)

The selection of the pilot sites was made taking into account the geographical distribution as well as the availability of data. Five eLTER Facilities have been chosen to test the WP4 approach to information clusters:

- Cairngorms (<https://deims.org/5a04fee1-42aa-47e9-abfc-043a3eda12ac>)
- TERENO Harz/Central German Lowland LTER (<https://deims.org/d6ce4453-17a8-49d8-9c02-caae8b6629a6>)
- LTER Zone Atelier Alpes - France (<https://deims.org/79d6c1df-570f-455f-a929-6cfe5c4ca1e9>)
- Doñana Long-Term Socio-ecological Research Platform - Spain (<https://deims.org/bcbc866c-3f4f-47a8-bbbc-0a93df6de7b2>)
- Gran Paradiso National Park (<https://deims.org/e33c983a-19ad-4f40-a6fd-1210ee0b3a4b>)

The RS data was prepared and uploaded to the DataLabs and will be available for visualisation in EcoSense. This included code in the R programming environment and data covering the above sample eLTER sites. NDVI and Land Surface Temperature (LST) datasets were acquired from the NASA MODIS satellite covering the decade from 2010 - 2020. Plots of average NDVI and average LST for each site were prepared. Following the data harvesting, the data layers must be cropped to the boundary of the sites or the platform to make the information available for successive integration in research activities at site scales. The resulting cropped datasets and the code to prepare this data were all uploaded to DataLabs for use by the community (Figure 4). The code, originally meant to serve the purposes of RS data retrieval only, was then expanded and merged in ReLTER, a R package performing third parties data retrieval which will be described in more detail in Section 5.

The design and the pilot implementation of the workflows was intended to trigger the development of a new service by establishing the structures for incorporating information into eLTER DIP. We expect that such a service will contribute to broadening the scope of site-based research, facilitating access to relevant information, overcoming technical barriers among different knowledge domains, providing processing tools, and improving the sustainability of the eLTER service provision to various stakeholder categories.

There is actually an on-going activity in collaboration with the SOs working group, to identify and select more specific and/or complex variables, where the data provisioning needs further specifications before the service can be rolled out to a more considerable number of sites. This includes variables generated by satellite imagery acquisition from various platforms, temporal aggregations, and spatial resampling.

Figure 4: Screenshot of a R script containing the code to perform a cookie cutting of Corine land cover datasets

5.1 Static view: regular provision of selected variables

Third-party data of interest to the eLTER community and functional to implementing the Whole System Approach, including selected RS data and products, belongs to the retrieval-based SOs category. As for all the other variables in the SO list, the retrieval-based ones should be provided regularly. In this respect, RS data do not differ from legacy data, and the workflow for their retrieval can be described by the same diagram, Figure 5, which has been introduced specifically for legacy data to highlight the main components and actions involved in identifying, selecting, documenting, processing, and storing data and metadata for both the sources and the datasets. We refer the reader to the project deliverable D4.1 “Workflows for retrieval and harmonisation of legacy data” (Peterseil, J. et al., 2022), for further details on each step/component represented in the diagram.

We refer to this workflow as a “static view” of the data retrieval: the data and their data sources are identified in advance, and the temporal resolution of the data time series is such that the data can be regularly downloaded from their sources, processed as described in the diagram and stored by the CDN for all the sites.

However, it is worth noticing that, more than other types of data, RS products might be pretty demanding regarding processing power and storage capability, thus leading to increasing costs of regular service provisioning. That stimulated the search for alternative solutions and for a “dynamical” approach where the retrieval might be performed on-demand through a central service or executed directly by the users utilising tools specifically developed to allow access and download of selected retrieved-based SOs. This alternative “dynamical view” is described in the following section, and it addresses the research community mainly.

Figure 5: Generic workflow retrieving third parties' data (D4.1, Peterseil, J. et al., 2022)

6 Piloting retrieval Remote Sensing data and products: a “dynamical” view of the workflow

Carmela Marangi

Part of the piloting described in the previous section aimed to develop proper workflows and specify the needed IT support for the (semi) automated extraction of RS datasets and their visualisation at a low cost. That, in particular, applies:

- In case of variables not available regularly by the third-party service but yet included in the list of observations answering the eLTER community’s research needs.
- For observations occasionally needed to address specific issues of creating actionable knowledge in the context of the Whole System Approach.
- To test the provision of new data services that may arise from the internal research community or in agreement with recent environmental policies and sustainability goals.
- To facilitate the integration of community modelling tools.

In Figure 6, we illustrate the diagram of a possible workflow for the RS data retrieval that applies both to SOs and to datasets that might be accessed in a (semi) automated way by means of tools that have been designed and developed in the PLUS WP4 specifically to this purpose. The colour coding and the components in the diagram are the same as in the previous ones.

Figure 6: Workflow for the retrieval of remote sensing data and products, either retrieval-based SOs or data products accessible via dedicated apps.

The diagram has been generated adopting the view of the user browsing the data sources with the help of the eLTER visualisation tool and selecting the desired datasets among the ones made available as retrieval-based SOs (static view) or via dedicated tools hosted in the DataLabs (dynamical view).

In the following subsections we describe the tools that have been implemented and made available for several remote sensing data products coming from multiple sources: (a) PhenoApp, a Python application designed to browse and download phenological variables; (b) CrocoTile , an app that assists in identifying the most suitable tile(s) of SENTINEL earth observation data for a specific research site; (b) ReLTER, an R package to provide access to several remote sensing products including Corine Land Cover, LST, and NDVI.

6.1 Tools: GeeLTERMap

Ricardo Diaz-Delgado & Diego García Díaz

The GeeLTERMap python package has been created as a resource for scientists and site managers integrated into the eLTER network to evaluate the monitoring of long-term ecosystem variables. It was developed within the scope of the eLTER Plus and SUMHAL projects.

GeeLTERMap is based on the Geemap package, a Python API that allows access to Google Earth Engine (GEE) datasets and algorithms and provides an interactive map interface (Gorelick et al, 2017). Additionally, we have access to all alphanumeric and spatial information from the Elter sites thanks to DEIMS and its Python API, DeimsPy]. Furthermore, by enabling access to all relevant site-related information, we can establish custom filters for sites on which we wish to perform specific procedures.

Figure 7: GeeLTERMap technologies scheme

Our application includes three buttons integrated into a Geemap map environment (Wu, 2020). Each button provides access to one of the three primary tools described in the following below. Additionally, a form has been included inside the map as another button. This form allows users to submit their own data for validating satellite products.

A video tutorial illustrating the use of GeeLTERMap with all its tools has been recorded and made available online (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=unxqGwAcBfA&t=2439s>). The python package can be retrieved from PyPi: <https://pypi.org/project/geeltermap/>

6.1.1 PhenoApp

PhenoApp was created in conjunction with the eLTER Plus and SUMHAL projects as a tool for scientists and managers who are part of the eLTER network. This application enables users to monitor the long-term LSP of various types of vegetation covers. The application features a dynamic map (Figure 6) that permits site selection within the network to view phenological metrics for individual or grouped pixels. These metrics are generated using the Sentinel 2 image series with the Python libraries Ndvi2Gif and PhenoPY. Additionally, the application integrates the MODIS phenology products (MCD12Q2.006) and the Copernicus Sentinel 2 High Resolution Vegetation Phenology Product (HR-VPP). Additionally, the application features a form enabling users to submit phenology data acquired through direct observation or phenocameras, which will be utilized to validate the various products acquired via satellite.

Figure 8: A view of the map interface of the PhenoApp application

PhenoApp works with the datasets described in table 2. All these products can be downloaded directly from the app.

Table 2: Summary of PhenoApp products.

Dataset	Satellite	Growing Cycles (*)	Start Year	Index	Spatial Resolution	Phenometrics
HR-VPP	Sentinel 2	2	2017	PPI	10 m	SOSD SOSV
MCD12Q2	MODIS	2	2001	EVI	500 m	MOSD MOSV

PhenoPy	Sentinel 2	1	2015	NDVI	10 m	EOSD EOSV
---------	------------	---	------	------	------	--------------

(*) As we are interested in natural vegetation, we've only considered the main growing cycle per year.

6.1.2 FloodApp

FloodApp (Figure 9) is a tool for obtaining the flooded surface of eTER sites. The tool design includes the complete Landsat series from Landsat 4-TM to Landsat 9-OLI, which provides data from 1984 until now, along with Sentinel 2, which provides data from 2017, as datasets.

The tool also enables obtaining pixel-wise statistics if the selected study period covers multiple images. The statistics include the minimum, maximum, mean, median, and percentiles of 10th, 20th, 90th, and 95th for different water indices. Water indices available are NDWI (McFeeters 1996), NDWI (Gao et al. 2015), MNDWI (Xu 2006) and AWEI (Feyisa et al. 2014). SWIR-2 band has also been added to the list of water indices since we have been detected and tested, and this band offers a very good quality water mask in marshland areas. The user can also set a threshold to identify the index cutoff value that closely corresponds to the actual flooded area.

Figure 9: FloodApp main interface (Braila Island median flood for 2022 in the example)

Scenes could be filtered based on cloud cover to exclude those with a high percent of cloud cover over the area. Also note that two RGB compositions of the chosen period are added to the map along with the water index, though the display is disabled by default. This enables comparison of flooding.

All the technical issues of the available datasets and statistics are summarized in the table below. And last, a new reminder that a video tutorial of GeeLTERMap demonstrating this entire process can be found in this link (GeeLTERMap).

Table 3: FloodApp products summary.

Dataset	Water Indexes	Start Year	Temporal Resolution	Spatial Resolution
Sentinel 2	NDWI (McFeeters) NDWI (Gao) MNDWI	2017	5 days	10 m
Landsat 4-9 (TM, ETM+, OLI)	AWEI SWIR-2	1984	8 days	30 m

6.1.3 LSTApp

The Land Surface Temperature tool (Figure 10) utilizes Google Earth Engine to access MODIS (MOD11A1) and Landsat (TIRS) datasets. Technical details of both datasets are shown in Table 4.

Figure 10: LSTApp main interface (Gran Paradiso median LST for 2022 in the example)

Our tool provides users with options to select the desired site, collection, start and end dates, filter by scene cloud coverage for Landsat and quality band for MODIS, and choose the band and statistic for image reduction in the desired timeframe. Likewise for the PhenoApp and FloodApp a legend can be displayed if desired on the screen. Like the other two tools, users can download data obtained from the LSTApp. Just consider that limitations set by the platform may prevent downloading a complete scene at a high spatial resolution, but users can always download an area of interest using the map drawing tools. The GeeLTERMap video tutorial explains this process in detail.

Table 4: LSTApp products summary.

Dataset	Bands	Start Year	Temporal Resolution	Spatial Resolution
MODIS MOD11A1	LST_Day LST_Night Emissivity	2001	5 days	1 km
Landsat 8-9 SR TIRS	ST_B10 Emissivity	2013	8 days	30 m (*100 m native resolution)

6.1.4 FormApp

We can generate water masks, Land Surface Temperature (LST) and phenometrics products for all the Elter sites in a relatively straightforward manner. However, we lack knowledge of the true terrain conditions beyond Doñana. Obtaining the actual terrain data from the staff at each site is hence essential. That is the reason why we have implemented a new tool that allows users to easily upload real ground truth data for each product. This simple tool collects the uploader's name and email, along with the originating site for the data. Users also have the ability to upload specific data to a "validation_data.txt" file, which will be used for validation purposes. FormApp also provides the option to upload a CSV file containing numerous observations, which will subsequently be utilized for validating our products.

Figure 11: FormApp main interface

6.1.5 Implementation in DataLabs and usage

Our three tools are located in the DataLabs and can be accessible in this link: <https://datalab.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk/resource/elter/pyvpp/tree/>

On the main Geeltermap site within the Datalabs, there is a notebook for each tool, an example CSV file, some NDVI products of Doñana for reference with Ndvi2Gif, and two text files, one containing links to video tutorials for the tools mentioned in this document and the other one containing the validation data that can be uploaded from the FormApp.

Figure 12: GeelTERMap site view within DataLabs

6.1.5.1 PyVPP

In order to download Copernicus High Resolution Vegetation Phenology and Productivity products from the [Wekeo platform](#), we have also developed a Python package that allows both: the use of local shapefiles or direct use of the DEIMS.ID of any eLTER site to search, download, mosaic, and crop the Sentinel 2 HR-VPP tiles with the input site boundaries.

This package is called PyVpp and it could be installed from the official Python Package Index repository (<https://pypi.org/project/pyvpp/>). A screenshot appears in Figure 12.

The screenshot shows the PyPi repository page for the 'pyvpp' package. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Buscar proyectos' and a magnifying glass icon. To the right, there are links for 'Ayuda', 'Patrocinadores', 'Acceder', and 'Registrarse'. The main header features the package name 'pyvpp 0.1.5' in large blue text, a green button with a checkmark and the text 'Versión más reciente', and a green button with a copy icon and the text 'pip install pyvpp'. Below the header, there is a grey box with the text 'Python package to download phenological data from Wekeo (HR-VPP datasets from Sentinel 2)'. The page is divided into two columns. The left column, titled 'Navegación', contains a menu with 'Descripción de proyecto' (highlighted), 'Histórico de versiones', and 'Archivos de descarga'. Below this, there is a section 'Enlaces del proyecto' with links for 'Homepage' and 'Repository'. At the bottom of the left column, there is a section 'Estadísticas' showing 'Estadísticas de GitHub:' and 'Estrellas: 3'. The right column, titled 'Descripción de proyecto', contains the heading 'PyVPP' and a paragraph of text: 'Python package to download data from the Pan European High Resolution Vegetation Phenology and Productivity part of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS). This package have been developed within the framework of the eLTER H2020 and SUMHAL projects, as a tool aimed at scientists and managers of the sites integrated in the eLTER network, for which long-term phenology monitoring can be assessed.' Below the text, there are two logos: 'eLTER PLUS' and 'SUMHAL Sustainability for Mediterranean Hotspots in Andalusia integrating LifeWatch ERIC'.

Figure 12: Screenshot of PyPi repository of the PyVPP python library

To enhance the usability of PyVPP, a video tutorial has been produced to describe the tool's usage with specific attention paid to elder staff. The tutorial can be accessed through the link: <https://youtu.be/LpmaqW1mBXM>.

6.1.5.2 Ndvi2Gif

Ndvi2Gif (Figure 13) is a python library designed to create Seasonal Composites of some standard EO indexes, based on several statistics applied to some Remote Sensings datastes. This tool uses Google Earth Engine API and Geemap python package to create seasonal compositions based on different statistics.

This tool has been updated in the framework of eLTER H2020 and SUMHAL projects, as the main input to the PhenoPy python package, which is the library that we use to get the phenometrics derived from the seasonal composites.

Buscar proyectos

Digdgeo

ndvi2gif 0.0.6

✓ Versión más reciente

Publicación: 20 oct 2023

`pip install ndvi2gif`

Python package to create seasonal composites of NDVI or several more vegetation, water, snow, etc. indexes, and download them as pretty gifs or geotiff rasters

Gestionar proyecto

Navegación

- Descripción de proyecto
- Histórico de versiones
- Archivos de descarga

Enlaces del proyecto

- Homepage

Estadísticas

Estadísticas de GitHub:

- ★ Estrellas: 23
- 🔗 Bifurcaciones: 10
- 📄 Open issues: 0
- 🔧 Open PRs: 0

Consulte estadísticas de este proyecto en [Libraries.io](https://libraries.io) o a través de [nuestro conjunto de datos público en Google BigQuery](#)

Metainformación

Licencia: MIT

Autor: [Diego García Díaz](#)

Requiere: Python >=3.8

Descripción de proyecto

Ndvi2Gif is a python library to create Seasonal Composites based on several statistics applied to some Remote Sensings datasets. This tool uses [Google Earth Engine API](#) and the amazing [Geemap package](#), to create yearly compositions based on different statistics. We also have added `deimsPy` [<https://pypi.org/project/deims/>](https://pypi.org/project/deims/) to get the boundaries of all eLTER sites. So now, you can choose between a shapefile, a map draw or just use an eLTER DeimsID to get the boundaries for your seasonal composite index.

This tool have been updated in the framework of [eLTER H2020](#) and [SUMHAL](#) projects, as the main input to [PhenoPy](#) python package, which is the library that we use to get the phenometrics derived from the seasonal vegetation composites.

Figure 13: Ndvi2Gif python library main page

The stats included at this point are:

- Maximum
- Mean
- Median
- Percentile 90
- Percentile 95

The indexes available are:

- NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)
- EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index)
- SAVI (Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index)
- GNDVI (Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)
- AVI (Advanced Vegetation Index)

- NBRI (Normalized Burn Ratio Index)
- NDSI (Normalized Difference Snow Index)
- AEWI (Automated Water Extraction Index)

All the Ndvi2Gif features are summarised in table 5.

Table 5: Ndvi2Gif products scheme

Dataset	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Indexes	Temporary Availability	Stats
Landsat (Landsat Surface Reflectance collections merged from Landsat 4-TM to Landsat 9-OLI)	30 m	7 days	NDVI EVI SAVI GNDVI AVI	1984-Present	Maximum Minimum Mean Median Perc 90 Perc 95
Sentinel 2	10 m	5 days	NBRI NDSI	2015-Present	
Sentinel 1	14 m	6 days	AEWI AEWINSH	2014-Present	
MODIS MOD09A1	500 m	Daily		2001-Present	

By default, the maximum NDVI is used as a seasonal reducer to avoid clouds and cloud shadows. However, any combination of statistics and dataset can be used. The Landsat and MODIS datasets are surface reflectance (SR) data, while Sentinel 2 is top-of-atmosphere (TOA) reflectance data. This is because surface reflectance for Sentinel 2 has only been available since 2017, but TOA is available since 2015. You can also use Sentinel 1 SAR data to combine it with vegetation indices. This is only useful for crops, where a higher index intensity is related to a higher plant height.

The operation of Ndvi2Gif is based on Google Earth Engine reducers (Figure 3), which allow to obtain pixel-level statistics for a time series of images. In our case, we have predefined 3 temporal levels to group the scenes and obtain our seasonal composite:

- 1st level: Seasons of the year.
- 2nd level: Months of the year
- 3rd level: 2 weeks periods

Thus, thanks to Ndvi2Gif, it is possible to obtain seasonal composites with the value of the selected statistic for each pixel in all the images that have entered the selected period. It is therefore a very powerful tool, which in our case has allowed us to have NDVI (or any other index) values for each pixel periodically, which have been used as inputs to calculate the phenometrics. But also, thanks to the integration with deimsPY, it is possible to obtain very valuable information of each site, applying any of the indices mentioned above, and see how they have evolved over the years.

A video tutorial for the usage of Ndvi2Gif has also been created. It can be founded in the next link: [Ndvi2Gif Python Package](#)

6.2 Tools: CrocoTile

Ivo Offenthaler

CrocoTile is a tool that assists in identifying the most suitable tile(s) of SENTINEL earth observation data for a specific research site. Typically, it is easy to determine a tile that covers an area of 100×100 km². However, there are scenarios where the research site is extensive or comprises multiple scattered subsites that exceed the tile size. In such cases, a single tile may not be sufficient, or a tile located away from the subsites' centroid may better represent a specific attribute like habitat type. The tool has been developed by I. Manakos and E. Katsikis (2022) of the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Information Technologies Institute, within the eH2020-ESHAPE project, where it has been proposed as a solution for addressing these edge cases and a QGIS desktop application has been implemented.

The CrocoTile algorithm is written in R and uses the Shiny framework to serve it as a web application, hosted by the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology. The tool has been specifically designed for the eLTER sites. Users can select their research site of interest and download a bundle of initial and processed spatial features (shapefiles) and metadata (HTML) as it is shown in Figure 9.

site data [what's this?](#) [about](#)

Abisko National Park - Sweden ▾

Leaflet | Map tiles by Stamen Design, CC BY 3.0 — Map data © OpenStreetMap contributors

- site: **Abisko National Park - Sweden**
- site category: **D i**
- 4 overlapping SENTINEL tiles: **33WXS, 34WDA, 34WDB, 33WXR**
- most relevant tile: **33WXR**

[Download](#)

Figure 14. Example of application of CrocoTile to an eLTER site

6.3 Tools: ReLTER

Micha Silver, Alessandro Oggioni, Paolo Tagliolato

ReLTER is an R (Core Team 2022) package developed in the context of eLTER RI to aid researchers in accessing spatial and tabular data from several sources. The R software system consists of thousands of packages for spatial (Bivand 2021) and statistical analysis, together with a variety of options for visualisation. Therefore, eLTER researchers who adopt **ReLTER** can seamlessly integrate RS data with further analyses, both within the framework of an R workflow or exported for further analysis.

Developers of this software package also considered an additional advantage to choosing an open-source computing platform. The need to insist on reproducible analysis techniques has recently gained traction (Reinecke et al. 2022, Fienen and Bakker 2016). This new package keeps with the long-standing policy in R of coded scripts, thereby ensuring the analyses' reproducibility and durability. In future work, researchers will be able to understand the computation done and repeat the procedures when necessary.

The ROpenSci community software platform submitted the package for review as it was accepted in December 2022 (Figure 10). This achievement ensures that the package matches international coding standards and offers a stable and well-known repository for publishing the code: <https://github.com/ropensci/ReLTER/>.

The screenshot shows the landing page for the ReLTER R package on the ROpenSci platform. The page has a blue header with the ROpenSci logo and navigation links for 'Reference', 'Articles', and 'Changelog'. A search bar is located in the top right corner. The main content area features the title 'ReLTER' and a brief description: 'ReLTER is an R package that provides access to DEIMS-SDR, allowing to interact with software implemented by eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI) and improving the data/information shared among the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) network. This package was conceived within eLTER H2020 project and will help advance the development of European Long-Term Ecosystem Research Infrastructures (eLTER RI)'. Below this, a list of functions is provided, including 'retrieve the information about entities (e.g. sites, datasets, and activities) shared by DEIMS-SDR', 'elaborate the information of single site or merge info from national network sites or entire International LTER (ILTER) in order to provide maps, figures, graphs etc', 'interact with the ODSEurope managed by members of the Geo-harmonizer project', and 'improve the quality of the dataset'. A 'Citation' section is also present, providing the citation text: 'To cite ReLTER please use: Alessandro Oggioni, Micha Silver, Luigi Ranghetti & Paolo Tagliolato. (2023). ReLTER: An Interface for the 'eLTER' Community (v2.0). Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5576813'. On the right side, there are sections for 'Links' (Browse source code, Report a bug), 'License' (Full license, GPL (v= 3)), 'Community' (Contributing guide), 'Citation' (Citing ReLTER), 'Developers' (Alessandro Oggioni, Micha Silver, Paolo Tagliolato, Luigi Ranghetti), and 'Software Peer-Review' (Peer Reviewed).

Figure 15: The ReLTER landing page on ROpenSci.

The ReLTER package consists of the following categories of functions:

- Retrieve site information from DEIMS.org. Includes metadata for a chosen site identified by its DEIMS.ID, such as contact information, infrastructure, research topics, affiliations, and the

polygon boundary (when available). These all are returned as R objects for further analysis within a script or for export to a data file for examination in external software.

- Retrieve metadata at ILTER network level, such as research topics, observed properties, as well as lists of network sites by country.
- Prepare visualisations of sites (map of boundary), ILTER networks (country-wide point locations map), and pie charts of observed properties at an individual site.
- Retrieve third-party spatial data (See *Table 2*), clipped to site boundaries, such as time series of MODIS images, and raster data offered by EcoDataCube (<https://ecodatacube.eu/>)
- Extract tables of taxonomy data for species at a chosen site.
- Retrieve sensor observations and observation procedures from several web-based sensor data archives for a chosen site.
- Retrieve species occurrence data for a chosen site from several web-based data archives such as GBIF, OBIS, and iNaturalist.

All the above functions are documented within the package, and the help pages are accessible in the usual way. Help pages for all functions include a brief example showing the function's syntax.

All **ReILTER** functions return R objects. Thus, they can easily be incorporated into scripts to perform analyses in a broader scope. Furthermore, when necessary, these extracted data tables or spatial layers can be exported to any standard format for external software (*Table 2*).

Moreover, **ReILTER** functions return tables enriched by semantic tagging. Columns are associated with specific terms of Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) vocabularies term and their meaning, so that favours disambiguation, translation and potentially eases data fusion. Currently the vocabularies in use are: EnvThes (<https://vocabs.ilter-europe.net/envthes/en/>), some of the NERC Vocabularies (<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/>), and Darwin Core glossary (TDWG - <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>). Finally the **ReILTER** functions adopt the Units package (Pebesma et al., 2016), this allows it to be associated with a unit of measurement with a specific column, easily achieving unit of measurement conversion and data aggregation.

*Table 6: Third parties' data available through **ReILTER** and the Standard Observations (SOs) they can contribute to.*

Data	Source	tabular	spatial [resolution]	Standard Observation (SOs) code
eILTER Site metadata	DEIMS.org	✓	✓ [high]	General information (DEIMS) SOSOC_039
eILTER Network metadata	DEIMS.org	✓	✓ [high]	
eILTER Activity metadata	DEIMS.org	✓	✓ [high]	-
Species distribution	GBIF, iNaturalist, OBIS	✓		all SOs related with species abundance, species distribution, etc.
Species Taxonomy	WoRMS, PESI	✓		
Generic data	Zenodo	✓		-
Sensor Data	(any) Sensor Observation	✓	✓ [high]	all sensor based SOs

	Service (OGC - SOS)		
Vegetation Index	MODIS, USGS Earth explorer	✓ [low]	Vegetation phenology and Leaf Area Index - European scale (SOBIO_015) , Vegetation phenology – site scale (SOBIO_016) , Leaf area index - forests (site scale SOBIO_025) , and Leaf area index – non-forested sites (SOBIO_026)
Land Surface Temperature	MODIS, USGS Earth explorer	✓ [low]	Physical and chemical water characteristics (SOHYD_005) and Soil temperature (SOHYD_168) Meteorological data (SOATM_027)
Other MODIS products	MODIS, USGS Earth explorer	✓ [low]	-
Landcover (Corine and others)	EUMAP EcoDatacube	✓ [high]	Land cover, land use, land cover change, land use change (SOSOC_036)
Copernicus-OSM buildings	EUMAP EcoDatacube	✓ [high]	Buildings and other structures (SOSOC_131)
Natura2000	EUMAP EcoDatacube	✓ [high]	-
Vegetation Index	EUMAP EcoDatacube	✓ [high]	Vegetation phenology and Leaf Area Index - European scale (SOBIO_015) , Vegetation phenology – site scale (SOBIO_016) , Leaf area index - forests (site scale SOBIO_025) , and Leaf area index – non-forested sites (SOBIO_026)
Forest cover	EUMAP EcoDatacube	✓ [high]	Vegetation aboveground biomass - forest (site scale SOBIO_023)

7 Demonstrations and capacity building

Micha Silver, Diego García Díaz

Following the first workshop that was held in Lyon, France, in February 2022, the developers suggested to project coordination to continue initiating training sessions as the package functionality grows. Future training can focus on incorporating the package into more complex workflows for RS analyses by using the extensive collection of r-spatial functionality within the R programming language.

7.1 PhenoApp demonstration

PhenoApp was presented by Diego García Díaz in the eLTER *Software workshop - Introducing new tools* that was held in Lyon, France, on February 7-9th, 2023 (Figure 11). This meeting allowed first contact with some PIs from different sites who have phenological data and are interested in validating with the satellite-derived data offered with PhenoApp. What is one of the main goals of PhenoApp: Cross-validation of in-situ and satellite data.

Figure 11: The PhenoApp presentation from the Lyon workshop

7.2 ReLTER demonstration

The **ReLTER** package has been presented to eLTER colleagues, and stakeholders on three occasions. During the Mallorca conference in April 2022, a short introductory presentation was offered. Among the outcomes of that conference, participants expressed a need for in-depth training in all the remote sensing tools being developed in the context of WP 4.3. As a result, a three-day long workshop was initiated and led by plusWP5 (Shayli Dor-Haim, and Terhi Rasilo).

This workshop (Figure 12) was conducted at INRAE in Lyon, France, in February 2023. That venue allowed for presentations and hands-on training in coding, so participants experienced each tool. Some 25 researchers took part in hands-on exercises using the **ReLTER** package for various analyses of data from DEIMS-SDR and further third-party remote sensing data. These third-party archives included i.e., different global species occurrence data, remote sensing products from NASA MODIS, and high-resolution derived products from the OpenDataScienceEurope Initiative at

<https://ecodatacube.eu>. The **ReILTER** session was led by Alessandro Oggioni, Paolo Tagliolato, and Micha Silver.

Finally, during the eILTER Plus and eILTER PPP Consortia Meeting in Frankfurt in April 2023, a “bird’s eye view” of the package was presented to participants by Alessandro Oggioni. This presentation was intended to demonstrate the overall capabilities of the package and outline ongoing development of the package looking ahead to eILTER RI.

Figure 12: Lyon workshop participants

8 Future development

Micha Silver, Diego Garcia Díaz

8.1 PhenoApp - GeelTerMap

PhenoApp is already available in a pre-release version in this GitHub repository: <https://github.com/Digdgeo/PhenoAppLyon>. But this is just a previous version of the GeelTerMap Python Package that we are developing, which will include two other tools to get land surface temperature and water flood for eLTER sites. This Python package will be ready by summer of 2023. We also would like to participate in more training sessions to show the new Water Flood and Land Surface Temperature tools. Regarding the PyVpp python package, we will add more Copernicus datasets to the download options.

8.2 ReLTER

Currently, at version 2.1, the developers of **ReLTER** will follow the needs of eLTER RI researchers and will continue adding new functionality and releasing new versions as required. This will include functions to prepare time series of RS data sets in line with future requirements from RI projects. Additional training workshops will also be offered pending requests from eLTER RI. In addition, the package developers intend to prepare a short paper for publication in a suitable peer-reviewed journal to announce and describe the innovations of this package.

9 Conclusions

The tools and workflows presented herein should be considered as enabling technologies. Hopefully, researchers and stakeholders from across the eLTER network will recognize the breadth of historic RS data currently available along timelines and over various spectral bands. Looking to the future, the exponentially increasing data acquisitions from new satellites present challenges and opportunities that were unavailable only two decades ago.

Therefore, modern ecological research cannot thrive on predefined, static variables. The dynamic workflow presented in this work and supported by a toolbox of flexible software applications are the mainstay of all future long-term ecological projects. The authors hope that moving toward eLTER RI, this approach, consisting of flexible and extensible analyses of RS data, will become part of the groundwork for future eLTER research projects.

Acknowledgements and project reference

The work was performed within the project eLTER PLUS (Grant agreement No. 871128), funded under the Horizon 2020 programme. The research challenges and science cases contributed to the definition of the requirements for the data sources and the selection of sites and variables included in the pilot. Both WP10 and WP11 supported the implementation of the demonstrators and the workflow design. The work was aligned with the requirements defined by the eLTER PPP project, especially those associated with the data services provider.

10 References

- Dirnböck, T., Peterseil, J., Forsius, M., Holmberg, M., Kühn, I., Futter, M., Vereecken, H. & Méndez, P. (2020). "Report about data requirements (CS1-4) to be used in VA and WP10". Deliverable D9.5 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128.
- Dorren, Luuk K.A, Berger, Frédéric, Imeson, Anton C, Maier, Bernhard, Rey, Freddy (2004). "Integrity, stability and management of protection forests in the European Alps", *Forest Ecology and Management*, 195(1-2), pp 165-176, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2004.02.057>.
- Koivula, H., Wohner, C., Rennie, S., Brown, M., Bolton, W., Magagna, B., Peterseil, J., Zilioli, M., Tagliolato, P., Oggioni, A. & Watkins, J.(2022). "Concept and extension of central data node capabilities". Deliverable D11.2 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128.
- Bivand, Roger. 2021. "Progress in the R ecosystem for representing and handling spatial data." *Journal of Geographical Systems* 23 (10). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10109-020-00336-0>.
- Core Team, R. 2022. "R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing." R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Fienen, Michael, and Mark Bakker. 2016. "HESS Opinions: Repeatable research: what hydrologists can learn from the Duke cancer research scandal." *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 20. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-20-3739-2016>.
- García-Díaz, D., Díaz-Delgado, R. 2023. PhenoApp. A Google Earth Engine based tool for monitoring phenology. *Revista de Teledetección*, 61, 73-81. <https://doi.org/10.4995/raet.2023.18767>
- Haase, P., Tonkin, J.D., Stoll, S., Burkhard, B., Frenzel, M., Geijzendorffer, I.R., Häuser, C., Klotz, S., Kühn, I., McDowell, W.H., Mirtl, M., Müller, F., Musche, M., Penner, J., Zacharias, S., Schmeller, D., 2018. "The next generation of site-based long-term ecological monitoring: Linking essential biodiversity variables and ecosystem integrity". *The Science of the total environment* 613-614, 1367-1384.
- Halada, L., Dick, J., Bolton, W., Gašparovičová, P., Hilbert, H., Baránková, Z., Gemmelová, L., Kozelová, I., Kenderessy, P., Rusňák, T., "Workflow for retrieval and harmonisation of data from official statistics", Deliverable D4.2 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128.
- Manakos, I., Katsikis, E. (2022) "Site Selection Methodology – Living Document". <https://elter-crocodile.datalabs.ceh.ac.uk/data/Methods.pdf>
- Peterseil, J., Djukic, I., Oggioni, A., Zilioli, M., Tagliolato, P., Bolton, W., Wohner, C., Marangi, C., Poppe, C., Provenzale, A., Baronetti, A., Parisi, A., Pons, M.-N. (2022). "Workflows for retrieval and harmonisation of legacy data". Deliverable D4.1 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128. 62pp + Annexes (1-5).
- Reinecke, Robert, Tim Trautmann, Thorsten Wagener, and Katja Schüler. 2022. "The Critical Need to Foster Computational Reproducibility." *Environ. Res. Lett.*
- Schentz, Herbert, Peterseil, Johannes, Magagna, Barbara, Mirtl Michael, (2011). "Semantics in Ecosystem Research and Monitoring". *EnvironInfo* 2011: 330-342
- Skiba, U, Vicente, J, Lomba, A, Diaz-Pines, E, Nikolaidis, N, Gaube, V, Haase, P, Dirnböck, T, Peterseil, J (2020). "Report on data requirements (CS1-4) to be used in VA and WP10". Deliverable D8.5 EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128

- Vitor C.F., Gilberto R. Queiroz, and Karine R. Ferreira. 2020. "An Overview of Platforms for Big Earth Observation Data Management and Analysis." *Remote Sensing* 12 (8).
<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12081253>.
- Wu, Q. 2020. "Geemap: A Python package for interactive mapping with Google Earth Engine". *The Journal of Open Source Software*, 5(51), 2305. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.02305>
- Wohner, C., Peterseil, J., & Klug, H. (2022). "Designing and implementing a data model for describing environmental monitoring and research sites". *Ecological Informatics*, 70, [101708].
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2022.101708>
- Wulder, Michael A., Jeffrey G. Masek, Warren B. Cohen, Thomas Loveland, and Curtis Woodcock. 2012. "Opening the archive: How free data has enabled the science and monitoring promise of Landsat." *Remote Sensing of the Environment* 122.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.01.010>.
- Zacharias, S. et al. (2022). Discussion paper on eLTER Standard Observations (eLTER SOs). Deliverable D3.1, Version 2.0, EU Horizon 2020 eLTER PLUS Project, Grant agreement No. 871128

Online resources

Destination Earth - <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/destination-earth>

List of figures

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the role of the eLTER Information Clusters in the project context.	9
Figure 3: General workflow to identify a data source and contribute it to DAR.	16
Figure 4: Screenshot of a R script containing the code to perform a cookie cutting of Corine land cover datasets.....	19
Figure 5: Generic workflow retrieving third parties' data (D4.1, Peterseil, J. et al., 2022)	21
Figure 6: Workflow for the retrieval of remote sensing data and products, either retrieval-based SOs or data products accessible via dedicated apps.	22
Figure 7: GeeLTERMap technologies scheme	23
Figure 8: A view of the map interface of the PhenoApp application.....	24
Figure 9: FloodApp main interface (Braila Island median flood for 2022 in the example).....	25
Figure 10: LSTApp main interface (Gran Paradiso median LST for 2022 in the example)	26
Figure 11: FormApp main interface	27
Figure 12: GeeLTERMap site view within DataLabs.....	28
Figure 12: Screenshot of PyPi repository of the PyVPP python library	29
Figure 13: Ndvi2Gif python library main page	30
Figure 14. Example of application of CrocoTile to an eLTER site.....	32
Figure 15: The ReLTER landing page on ROpenSci.....	33
Figure 11: The PhenoApp presentation from the Lyon workshop	36
Figure 12: Lyon workshop participants.....	37

List of tables

Table 1: The main public RS data and service providers as listed in the ESA's website.	17
Table 2: Summary of PhenoApp products.	24
Table 3: FloodApp products summary.	26
Table 4: LSTApp products summary.	27
Table 5: Ndvi2Gif products scheme	31
Table 6: Third parties' data available through ReLTER and the Standard Observations (SOs) they can contribute to.	34